

Changing determinants of international conservation funding committed to major deforestation regions in South America ¹

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Abstract

International conservation funding to low- and middle-income countries has increased significantly in recent years. However, understanding of the underlying factors driving the geographic distribution of such funding remains limited. This study aimed to identify the relative importance of five factors (i.e., conservation targets, threat levels, costs, Indigenous Peoples and local communities, and preexisting investment) that potentially influence conservation funding allocation at the subnational level in major deforestation regions of South America between 1987 and 2013. Overall, we found that funding was mainly allocated to remote areas with high species richness and carbon storage, while areas with high threat levels were often overlooked, especially until 2008. After 2008, international donors committed more funding to areas with high carbon storage, but not areas with high species richness, suggesting the prominence of climate-related concerns over biodiversity conservation. Although often advocated, we did not find evidence supporting Indigenous Peoples and local communities being important in explaining funding allocation. However, we identified a strong preference for the Amazon as a charismatic ecoregion. Our findings underscore the diverse and changing factors that drive conservation funding, highlighting the importance of subnational analyses in aligning international conservation funding with local conservation needs from the perspectives of different actors. We hope that our study will contribute to the ongoing conversation on diverse values in conservation and inform decision-making for future funding allocations.

Introduction

Conserving the world's biodiversity and its various contributions to society is a major challenge of our times (IPBES, 2019; Secretariat of the CBD, 2000). The magnitude of the conservation challenge makes it difficult to ensure sufficient funding to slow down or halt biodiversity loss, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Deutz et al., 2020). In response to the gap between local challenges and available resources for conservation, multiple and substantial multilateral agreements and commitments have been made to address conservation challenges internationally, and have become a major source of funding for conservation in low- and middle-income countries (Deutz et al., 2020; Waldron et al., 2013). In the first decade of the 21st century, lower-income countries received almost as much international conservation funding as their domestic conservation spending (Kuemmerle et al., 2019; Waldron et al., 2013). Still, there is a huge gap between the funding needed to address conservation challenges and the funding committed (Clark et al., 2018), making the question of where funding should be allocated a central question in conservation science and practice (Deutz et al., 2020; Lovejoy, 2020). Specifically, it is important to understand the allocation of international conservation funding, as funding from the global north is expected to play a major role in filling the funding gap in lower-income mega-biodiverse countries, and is often allocated in a decentralized and uncoordinated way (Kuemmerle et al., 2019).

Conservation scientists have made multiple suggestions on where to prioritize conservation action, considering various factors including conservation targets, threat levels, costs, recognition of and support for Indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLC), and preexisting investment. For instance, one can expect the distribution of conservation funding to focus on high stocks of conservation targets (e.g., high biodiversity) (Brooks et al., 2006; Jung et al., 2021), or on areas where threat levels are high (e.g., high deforestation rates) hence requiring conservation interventions (Brooks et al., 2006; Myers et al., 2000; Rodrigues et al., 2006), or on areas where they can be used most cost-effectively, given limited resources (Armsworth, 2014; Naidoo et al., 2006). Additionally, conservation has been increasingly emphasizing the recognition and support of IPLC, for both their stewardship of nature and the co-benefit of secured and improved livelihood for these communities (Dawson et al., 2021; Garnett et al., 2018; Lauriola, 2003; Lovejoy, 2020).

Empirical analyses of the geography of conservation funding are evolving, and existing work suggests that all the aforementioned factors might be important. For prevalence of conservation targets, funding distribution correlates well with species richness at both country level and protected area level (Brockington and Scholfield, 2010; Miller et al., 2013) and with carbon storage and sequestration at country level (Halimanjaya, 2016). Regarding threats, the richness of threatened species and higher deforestation rates are associated with more funding at the country level (Bare et al., 2015; Miller et al., 2013) and protected area level (Nakamura Lam, 2017). However, areas with higher threat levels were sometimes sacrificed given the higher cost to conserve them and their often reduced conservation value given the destruction (Hecht, 2005; Tesfaw et al., 2018). Cost-wise, remote places have historically been preferred for establishing protected areas or projects to reduce deforestation, due to lower land prices hence lower opportunity costs (Baldi et al., 2017; Delacote et al., 2022; Joppa and Pfaff, 2009) but more accessible places were reported to be more likely to host conservation research and projects given the lower logistic cost (dos Santos et al., 2015; Malhado et al., 2020). IPLC have been historically ignored when allocating conservation funding (Lauriola, 2003), and it is

unclear whether the calls for recognizing and supporting IPLC in conservation have systematically improved their likelihood of getting funded (Garnett et al., 2018; Schwartzman and Zimmerman, 2005; Stevens, 1997). Finally, evidence suggests that previous conservation investments attract follow-up conservation efforts and funding due to established relations, institutions, infrastructure, or accumulated knowledge (Abeygunawardane et al., 2022; Ahrends et al., 2011; Pinnschmidt et al., 2021).

Building on this body of work, we address three knowledge gaps. First, it is unclear how these factors collectively influence the allocation of international conservation funding, particularly when considering multiple types of conservation interventions beyond protected areas. Second, given that most studies have focused on either country-level or protected area-level scales, our understanding of how international funding is allocated at the subnational level is highly incomplete, even though these scales are most important for conservation planning and action (Nakamura Lam, 2017). Finally, while research identified specific thematic preferences of different donors given their social, economic, political, and geographical connections, it is unclear if and how donor-specific preference affected their consideration of these general factors when allocating funding at the subnational level (Halimanjaya, 2016; Qin et al., 2022). Assessing the importance of factors potentially influencing conservation funding allocation, at subnational scales and by donor groups, can provide important insights into how conservation funding is allocated at a scale relevant to conservation planning (EC. JRC, 2021; Nakamura Lam, 2017).

South America's major deforestation regions provide an interesting case to understand the spatial distribution of international conservation funding in relation to the five key factors discussed so far. These ecoregions (including the Amazon, Atlantic Forests, Pantanal, Caatinga, Cerrado, Gran Chaco, and Chiquitano Forests) host astonishing biodiversity and store massive amounts of carbon (Da Silva et al., 2001; Leal et al., 2005; Pötzschner et al., 2022; Soto-Navarro et al., 2020). Diverse groups of IPLC live there, and many have been stewarding nature for a long time (BenYishay et al., 2017; Garnett et al., 2018); and their livelihoods depend on healthy ecosystems (Levers et al., 2021; Walker et al., 2020). At the same time, these regions have been heavily threatened by habitat destruction, especially due to deforestation driven by commercial agriculture (Curtis et al., 2018; Fehlenberg et al., 2017; Kaimowitz and Smith, 2001; Sy et al., 2015). Thus, they have high conservation importance and, combined with high and rising threats, are rendered major hotspots of international conservation focus (Zimmerer, 2011). As a result, the past decades have seen growing international funding for nature conservation in South America (de La Mata and Riega-Campos, 2014; Gomes et al., 2018; Qin et al., 2022). However, the distribution of international conservation funding varies considerably over space and among donors (Correa et al., 2019; Qin et al., 2022).

Here, we used the database of international public funding for conservation-related projects in Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, and Paraguay between 1975 and 2013 (AidData, 2017; Qin et al., 2022) to provide the first quantitative assessment of the factors influencing the subnational-level allocation of international conservation funding to South America's threatened ecoregions. We ask two overarching research questions:

- 1) How do conservation targets, threat levels, costs, IPLC lands, and pre-existing conservation investments relate to the geographic distribution of international conservation funding?
- 2) How does the association between international conservation funding and these factors change across major donor groups?

Using a Bayesian multi-level modeling framework, we empirically explored five hypotheses explaining the geographic distribution of conservation funding at subnational level: H1: Donors commit more funding to areas with higher prevalence of conservation targets; H2: Donors commit more funding to areas with intermediate threat levels, as areas with low threat levels might not require conservation funding and areas with high threat levels might be seen as too expensive to invest in; H3: Donors commit less funding to intermediately remote areas, as more remote areas have low opportunity cost and more accessible areas entail low logistical costs to conserve; H4: Donors commit more funding to areas managed by IPLC, as these areas are more likely to deliver benefits for both biodiversity conservation and local communities' rights and livelihood; and H5: Donors commit more funding to areas with higher levels of preexisting conservation investment, given existing relationships, infrastructure, and knowledge. We then compared the influence of these factors between the major (groups of) donors.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area and datasets

Our study area consisted of tropical moist and dry forest ecoregions in Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, and Paraguay (Olson et al., 2001). A previous study compiled a database of international conservation funding committed to the area between 1975 and 2013 (Qin et al., 2022). This dataset combines keyword search and manual review to extract conservation-related projects from a dataset of bilateral and multilateral grants and loans (AidData, 2017), which resulted in 1947 conservation projects from 33 bilateral and multilateral donors. In this study, we excluded loans from the aforementioned database, because loans tended to encompass a small number of projects with a large volume of funding and likely emphasized development rather than conservation. The remaining grants included 1852 projects with a total funding volume of about 2.72 billion USD, committed between 1985 and 2013 (Data S1). Among them, 1070 (58 %) projects with a funding volume of 1.995 billion USD (73 %) were georeferenced, with the left-out 27 % being outside of the tropical forest region (e.g., for conservation in Patagonia) or without enough information to be allocated to the subnational level. Combining the amount of funding committed to these projects and the area of interest indicated by these projects, we calculated the total amount of funding committed to conservation-related projects per area (US\$/km²).

To explain the geographic patterns of conservation funding allocation, we assembled spatial variables representing five factors associated with our five hypotheses: H1) the prevalence of conservation targets, H2) threat levels, H3) costs, H4) IPLC lands, and H5) preexisting investment. For conservation targets, we used species richness and carbon density. We used species richness data calculated from range maps of mammals, birds, and amphibians, with data from the International Union for the Conservation of Nature, NatureServe, and BirdLife International (Jenkins et al., 2013; Pimm et al., 2014). Carbon density consisted of both above- and below-ground biomass carbon in 2010 (Soto-Navarro et al., 2020). Note that while forest cover may play a role in determining conservation funding, we chose not to include it as a conservation target, because it can be highly correlated with carbon density, and the growing interest in forests is largely intertwined with the interest in carbon in the context of climate finance. For threat level, we considered two variables: the richness of threatened species and the threat of habitat loss. Threatened species richness was calculated by overlaying the ranges of threatened species (mammals, birds, amphibians) as listed by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (Jenkins et al., 2013). Given our focus on deforestation regions and forest/woodland ecoregions, we used forest loss to approximate the threats of habitat loss,

which was calculated as the area experiencing forest loss in each 30 km × 30 km grid cell between 2001 and 2007 (Hansen et al., 2013). As funding allocated after 2001 accounts for about 90 % of total funding volume covered in our data (Data S1), deforestation between 2001 and 2007 should be relevant to most of the funding decision analyzed in this study. Considering the literature on the triage or sacrifice of the most deforested area (Brannstrom, 2009; Oliveira and Hecht, 2016), we included the squared term of forest loss as a predictor to test a possible nonlinear, quadratic relationship between forest loss and funding. To approximate the cost, we used the remoteness variable, measured by the average travel time of the sample grid cell to the nearest megacity in 2000 (Nelson, 2008). Here, land rent hence the opportunity cost for conservation increases with remoteness, while logistic cost decreases with remoteness. As different conservation interventions and different donors/projects may emphasize minimizing opportunity cost vs. logistic cost (Abeygunawardane et al., 2022; Joppa and Pfaff, 2009; Malhado et al., 2020), we included the squared term of remoteness to test if the combined preferences would lead to a curved relationship of less funding in intermediate remoteness. We used IPLC lands or settlements data from national governments to calculate the percentage of IPLC land in the sample grid cell (DGEEC, 2012; FUNAI, 2019; INAI, 2017; INCRA, 2019; INRA, 2012). Finally, for preexisting investment, we used funding committed until 2008 as the independent variable and funding committed after 2008 (i.e., from 2009) as the dependent variable (Fig. S1). All variables were projected to an Albers Equal Area projection and summarized to 30 km × 30 km grid cells – a size to minimize the effect of spatial autocorrelation in forest loss, while to capture conservation investment within an impactful distance to threats (Biggs et al., 2008; Negret et al., 2020). We then systematically sampled one out of every nine cells (i.e., the center 30 km × 30 km cell of every 90 km × 90 km) to reduce the effect of spatial autocorrelation in other variables. This sampling yielded a sample size of 1300 (Data S2).

2.2. Statistical modeling

We applied Bayesian models (van de Schoot et al., 2021) to estimate the influence of the variables capturing each of our five factors on the magnitude of international funding committed. We specified a multilevel model setting with varying effects between the two levels (Amazon vs. other), assuming that international interest might vary markedly between the Amazon and the other ecoregions (Mempel and Corbera, 2021; Qin et al., 2022). Additionally, while the Amazon is a meaningful predictor of funding distribution, simply adding an Amazon dummy in fixed-effects models could overshadow variations that might otherwise be explained by more contextual and fine-scale factors. This setup allowed us to estimate the global average effects, as well as region-specific variations in these effects, resulting in the following model:

$$y_i = \alpha_{\text{Region}i} + \beta_{\text{Region}i} * X_i$$

Here, y_i refers to the log-transformed and standardized volume of funding per area (\$/km²) assigned to each grid cell i over the study period, $\alpha_{\text{Region}[i]}$ is the region-varying effect intercept, $\beta_{\text{Region}[i]}$ is the region-varying effect slope, and X is the set of variables for which the effect is to be tested. We sampled 4000 realizations of the posterior distribution using Markov Chain Monte Carlo simulations with four sampling chains running for 2000 iterations and a warm-up period of 1000 iterations. Convergence was verified using the R statistic and examination of trace plots (Vehtari et al., 2021). We evaluated model fit based on posterior predictive checks (van de Schoot et al., 2021).

For hypotheses H1 to H4, we used overall funding as the dependent variable, and modeled different combinations of independent variables related to the factor being tested, with variables

related to other factors as control variables. We compared model performance based on out-of-sample predictive accuracy using the leave-one-out expected log predictive density with the R-package loo (Vehtari et al., 2022, Vehtari et al., 2017). For hypothesis H5, we used the funding volume committed after 2008 (i.e., from 2009) as the dependent variable and added the funding volume committed until 2008 as an additional independent variable. Finally, to test if donor-specific preferences can be explained by these general considerations and how their preferences differ from one another, we used funding from a more specific donor group/donor as the dependent variable for the best performing model for all funding. Specifically, we looked at funding committed by the three largest donor groups: Multilaterals [e.g., Global Environmental Facility], bilateral donors in Europe, and bilateral donors in North America. We also looked at funding from Germany, Norway, and Spain, which are top bilateral donors in Western, Northern, and Southern Europe, respectively (Fig. 1). For all models, we also calculated the conditional effects of each factor when other factors were held at their mean. This allowed us to isolate the individual effect of variables (e.g. forest loss and remoteness) despite potential correlation between them. The modeling was performed using the R package brms (Bürkner, 2021) in R version 4.1.1 (R Core Team, 2021) as an interface to the Bayesian inference engine Stan (Carpenter et al., 2017).

3. Results

We found that conservation targets, threat levels, cost, and preexisting investment improved the model performance in explaining the conservation funding pattern, whereas including IPLC lands did not (Table 1). Within the conservation targets, we found that the model including species richness (model M1.1) had better results than the model using carbon density as the predictor (M1.2) (Table 1). The model that included both variables under the conservation targets (M1.3) showed the best predictive accuracy. Regarding threat level, using either threatened species richness (M2.1) or forest loss (M2.2) improved prediction accuracy; however, including the square term of forest loss (M2.3) to identify the intermediate influence of threat did not improve model performance. The combination of both the variables (M2.4) outperformed the other options. In terms of cost, considering the remoteness of locations (M3.1) significantly improved the predictive accuracy. We did not detect a quadratic relationship between accessibility and the funding received (M3.2). Including IPLC land as an independent variable (M4.1) did not introduce a significant change in the model predictive accuracy. As for agglomeration effects, using the pre-2008 funding information improved the model (M5.1; with or without IPLC as control), but only marginally, as the standard error was almost equal to the difference between the expected log pointwise predictive density.

We plotted region-level coefficients for the best-performing model for all funding (M2.4) (Fig. 2a) and funding after 2008 (M5.1_wIPLC) (Fig. 2b). The influence of most variables differed significantly between the Amazon and other regions. In general, the variables had a non-zero influence on the level of funding committed outside of Amazon, while within Amazon, these influences were closer to zero (Fig. 2a). Outside the Amazon, funding was associated with higher levels of both species richness and carbon density, longer travel time, and lower levels of threats (less forest loss and fewer threatened species). Within the Amazon, higher carbon density was associated with more funding for conservation, but the influence of other factors was weak or neutral.

The positive association between high carbon density of the sample grid cell and funding was consistent for all funding vs. funding committed after 2008. By contrast, the threat-avoiding

tendency differed between the full period and after 2008. Throughout the study period, areas with more forest loss or threatened species tended to receive less funding; however, after 2008, areas with more forest loss did not receive less funding, and areas with more threatened species were more likely to receive funding. In addition, funding committed after 2008 showed a much larger preference towards the Amazon compared to other regions, and within the Amazon, emphasized carbon over biodiversity.

Comparing the observed and simulated data by the best-fitting model (i.e., M2.4), our model was able to capture the general preference of international conservation funding towards the Amazon, the Andes, and the Atlantic Forest (Fig. 3), and the avoidance of other areas receiving lower than average funding (e.g., Gran Chaco, Cerrado, Chiquitano). The model also captured noticeable trends within ecoregions, such as the emphasis on coastal regions of the Atlantic forests, and the lack of funding towards the south of the study area. However, our model did not explain well the much higher level of funding in Paraguay. To further test the importance of the Amazon as a charismatic ecoregion, we ran two extra models with only an Amazon dummy vs. the Amazon dummy plus all the identified variables as the independent variables. Adding the other variables would bring the fixed effect of the Amazon dummy from 0.795 (estimate error: 0.011) to 0.423 (estimate error: 0.031), suggesting the preference towards the Amazon can only be partially explained by the variations of our identified factors between Amazon and other regions.

We further tested how well the general factors depict the spatial preferences of specific donors (Fig. 4). Across the major group of donors, the variables identified in the best aggregate models (M2.4) captured the preference of multilateral donors and European donors (especially of Germany and Norway), showing that funding allocation decisions by those donors can mostly be explained by the factors we assessed in this study. The discrepancies between the model prediction and the observed distribution of funding committed by North America and Spain suggested that factors other than what we proposed dominated the funding allocation decisions of these donors.

The influence of different factors varied between the donor groups (Fig. 5). Although higher species richness is strongly associated with more conservation funding outside the Amazon for most donor groups, it did not show a positive connection with funding committed by Norway. In most cases, grid cells with higher carbon density were likely to receive more funding from European donors, but the trend was the opposite for multilateral funding outside of the Amazon. Multilateral funding focused more on threatened species richness within the Amazon, but more on all species richness outside the Amazon. Funding committed by Germany varied strongly within regions, and unlike the tendency of other donors, German funding preferentially went to areas with low remoteness. Norway's commitment mainly differed between the Amazon and other regions, with little within-region variation. We chose not to report the results for North America and Spain in Fig. 5, as the posterior predictive check (Fig. 4) suggested that the model predictions for these donors were not robust and ought to be interpreted with care.

4. Discussion

Tracking and explaining where conservation funding is allocated has been a key challenge for evaluating the effectiveness of conservation, and thus, for improving the allocation of limited conservation resources (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2021; Miller, 2014; Silva and Topf, 2020). Here, we provide the first continental-scale, subnational assessment of the drivers of international conservation funding across the major deforestation frontiers of

South America. Quantifying the individual and combined importance of five plausible alternative factors that potentially explain funding distribution, we found that international conservation funding has mainly flowed to areas with high levels of conservation targets and, to a lesser extent, areas that are remote or with lower levels of threat. We also identified the increasing importance of carbon density in attracting international conservation funding compared to biodiversity, remoteness, and threat levels. Pre-existing conservation investment had a slightly positive link with attracting more conservation funding, uncovering agglomeration effects. Surprisingly, IPLC lands was not an important factor explaining past funding allocation, despite IPLC land/environment rights and their stewardship for nature being advocated and potentially sought for in recent decades. Our analysis quantified a bias towards charismatic ecoregions, such as the Amazon in our case, in the allocation of international conservation funding. Finally, we uncovered donor-specific preferences, such as multilateral donors' interest in biodiversity and European donors' focus on carbon, and discussed the implications for allocating and accessing funding.

Our results showed that donors indeed commit more funding to areas with a higher prevalence of conservation targets (H1), both in terms of biodiversity and carbon. This trend is in line with findings at the national level and for individual PAs, where both biodiversity and carbon stocks have been found to guide the distribution of international conservation funding (Bare et al., 2015; Brockington and Scholfield, 2010; Halimanjaya, 2016; Miller et al., 2013). We also noticed an increasing importance of carbon as a factor explaining the allocation of conservation funding over time, as more funding was more likely to be associated with carbon stocks after 2008 rather than with high species richness (Fig. 2). While considerable co-benefits exist between conserving biodiversity and carbon (Law et al., 2021; Soto-Navarro et al., 2020), it is important to make sure relatively low-carbon but biodiversity-rich ecosystems are not neglected (Ravikumar et al., 2017; Thomas et al., 2013).

Our second hypothesis (H2: Donors commit more funding to areas with intermediate threat levels) was not supported by our results because including the squared term of forest loss did not improve model performance. Instead, we found a negative effect of the threat level (i.e., forest loss) on the allocation of conservation funding (Fig. 2). This contrasts with the positive correlation between the deforestation rate and conservation aid that has been shown in Sub-Saharan Africa at the country level (Bare et al., 2015) or in Peruvian protected areas (Nakamura Lam, 2017). A possible explanation for this could be that funding indeed went to countries and protected areas with higher deforestation risk, but at the subnational level avoided regions with high deforestation rates and areas outside protected areas – as we see in the case of Gran Chaco and Cerrado (Kuemmerle et al., 2017; Strassburg et al., 2017). Further investigation of such discrepancies would require a closer look at the spatial-temporal dynamics of both deforestation and conservation investment and could help to better understand why more conservation aid is not necessarily associated with a reduction in national deforestation rates (Bare et al., 2015).

Our models could not provide support for hypothesis H3 that donors commit less funding to intermediate remoteness areas, as including the squared term of the remoteness measure did not improve the model performance. Outside of the Amazon, the dominant pattern is the preference towards remote locations, suggesting that opportunity cost rather than logistic cost were more relevant in these areas, in line with a general preference for remote areas as reported by other studies (Baldi et al., 2017; Powers et al., 2013). Within the Amazon, remoteness showed no clear influence on committed funding volume, suggesting that the consideration of cost took

place at a later stage of project implementation, or that the balance between increasing logistic costs and decreasing opportunity costs with remoteness was, overall, neutral for this region.

We also found no evidence supporting hypothesis H4 that donors would commit more funding to areas managed by IPLC to leverage potential synergies between conserving biodiversity and supporting local people. Indeed, direct support to IPLC for climate and biodiversity conservation has been lacking (Rainforest Foundation Norway, 2021). However, the lack of even indirect funding for IPLC probably showed a lack of recognition of their critical role in conserving nature. The relatively weak consideration of IPLC in conservation funding allocation poses challenges to implementing recent pledges to directly support IPLC, as the mechanism to channel funding and the capacity to manage funding remains to be built (Cannon, 2022). Moreover, IPLCs in our study region have sometimes been relocated to make space for state conservation interventions (Lauriola, 2003; Tauli-Corpuz et al., 2020), and the IPLC land datasets we used would only reflect their current boundary but not the historical area that they customarily manage or places still under the demarcation process (UN-ECLAC, 2014), hence might not fully reflect the potential effect of IPLC stewarded lands in attracting conservation funding. Either of these explanations suggests the need for more just and inclusive decision-making in future allocation of conservation funding that recognizes and supports IPLC's stewarding of nature and their own needs.

We hypothesized that more funding is committed to areas with higher levels of preexisting conservation investment (H5), and we found some support for this, although the effect was weak. This might indicate a mix of continuing support for existing protected areas and changing conservation priorities (Adams et al., 2019). Such changes include the general shift from conserving biodiversity to conserving carbon (Jung et al., 2021; Thomas et al., 2013), the shift from investing in conserving remote and less threatened areas to more accessible areas with higher levels of threat (Mittermeier et al., 2011; Myers et al., 2000). Future research may explore if such shifts in priorities happened gradually over time, or abruptly due to major events such as the financial crisis or the establishment of the Amazon Fund in 2008/2009 (Correa et al., 2019).

Our results presented a clear preference for the Amazon, particularly for international conservation funding committed after 2008 (Fig. 2b), and by bilateral donors like Norway (Fig. 5e). The focus on the Amazon can be explained by its extraordinary conservation value in terms of biodiversity and carbon, as well as its relative remoteness and low levels of threat in many parts – all factors associated with higher funding in our analyses. However, the dominance of the Amazon went beyond what can be explained by these factors, suggesting that it resembles a ‘charismatic’ ecoregion that can mobilize donors similar to charismatic megafauna (Leader-Williams and Dublin, 2000; Mempel and Bidone, 2022). Worth noting that receiving countries can sometimes negotiate the funding committed to such region of interest to be used for conservation projects in adjacent regions. For instance, one of the largest bilateral funding channels, the Amazon Fund, was established in 2008 focusing on the Amazon biome in Brazil as the target geography, but was revised in 2016 to cover the entire Brazilian Amazon (legal Amazon), which also includes part of the Cerrado biome. Additionally, up to 20 % of the fund can be distributed to other parts of Brazil and other tropical forests outside of Brazil (Amazon Fund, 2021; Correa et al., 2019). The Amazon Fund example suggests some flexibility in shaping the targeted geography of funding at the commitment and distribution stage, and the possibility of recipients navigating and leveraging donor preferences to meet local conservation

needs. Future research can further explore the shift in geographic or thematic focus between different stages of international conservation funding (e.g., commitment, distribution, and implementation) to understand the interaction between actors and how it affects funding allocation and effectiveness.

Donor-level analysis provided further insight and could enable tailored recommendations for future funding allocation. Multilateral funding allocation was well predicted based on our set of independent variables (Fig. 4), suggesting that multilateral donors indeed follow the general global interests assessed in this study. While multilateral conservation funding focused on biodiversity-rich areas, it tended to avoid areas with more threatened species outside the Amazon (Fig. 5b). Previous research has suggested that infrastructure development projects funded by major multilateral donors were disproportionately likely to be located in areas with a high richness of threatened species (Morley et al., 2021). Thus, multilateral donors need to address the risk of neglecting threatened ecosystems and species in both conservation and development funding. Unlike multilateral donors with a strong focus on biodiversity, European donors have committed more funding to places with higher carbon density (Fig. 5c-e). The distribution of bilateral funding also deviated more from the model results compared to that of multilateral funding (Fig. 4), which indicated more specific concerns beyond the common factors we tested (Fig. 1). These specific preferences, represented in the geographic distribution of conservation funding, can be a combination of donor agendas and the integration of biodiversity conservation in development and climate finance decisions (Harvey et al., 2010; Qin et al., 2022). In either case, this can have real implications for access to funding and resources, particularly when international donor priorities are not geographically aligned with biodiversity or local people's needs (Ravikumar et al., 2017). The substantial influence of carbon and bilateral interests on conservation funding allocation observed in this study might speak to the recent call made by many developing countries, including Brazil, Argentina, and Bolivia, for a dedicated global biodiversity financing mechanism that would be more independent from bilateral and climate agendas (LMG-CBD, 2022). Yet, such a global biodiversity financing mechanism remains to receive enough support from the major donor countries (Zhu et al., 2022).

The analyses offer insights into why international conservation donors neglect certain ecoregions. First, many of South America's neglected but threatened ecoregions are dry forests and savannas (Alcorn et al., 2010; Dawson et al., 2021; Kuemmerle et al., 2017). These areas have lower biodiversity and carbon stocks than rainforests, experience high and rising human pressure (e.g., Gran Chaco and Cerrado), and are generally more accessible than the vast Amazonian landscape, all of which are associated with less funding in our analyses (Table 1, Fig. 2). Second, these funding 'cold spots' align well with research 'cold spots' (Hickisch et al., 2019), pointing to a reinforcing cycle between awareness and funding (Ahrends et al., 2011). Raising awareness of the understudied areas may require joint efforts to integrate the literature in different languages (Amano et al., 2021), recognize indigenous and local knowledge (Blackie et al., 2014), and improve awareness and assessment of the full spectrum of nature's contribution to humans (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2022). Given that the science community will likely have more flexibility than international funding agencies, more research on these cold spots can help break the cycle and bring more financial resources to neglected regions.

While we provide the most detailed analyses of conservation funding allocation to South America's deforestation regions, several caveats should be considered and can be improved

with future efforts. First, the funding volume per area we analyzed is not a direct measure of funding spent for conservation, but rather an indicator of the interest and resources committed by international donors to these areas. Expanding fine-scale tracking of conservation funding would help link funding with actions for more accurately measuring investments and impacts (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2021). Second, while we chose to focus on subnational-level factors, country-level differences such as GDP or bilateral relationship also influence funding allocation (Miller et al., 2013), which may explain the higher level of funding to Paraguay that was not captured by our model (Fig. 3). There are also potentially other factors influencing international funding decisions that are not covered within the scope of this study, including local ecosystem services, socioeconomic conditions, governance, and national politics and conservation strategies (Devkota et al., 2022; Miller, 2014). Further investigation to compare international funding distribution with domestic and local interests and needs can help reveal the how they have shaped and responded to one another. Third, our analyses carried over assumptions and uncertainties inherent in our predictor variables, such as a general underestimation of carbon stocks in dry forests (Pötzschner et al., 2022), uncertainties in biodiversity metrics (Crawford et al., 2021; Soto-Navarro et al., 2020), and the limited aspect of biodiversity represented by species richness. Fourth, we did not include protected areas as a predictor to avoid circularity, as funding might well flow to proposed protected areas, although the influence of protected areas on attracting funding may be partly covered by the effect of preexisting investment. Future work may investigate the influence of existing vs. planned conservation mechanisms, including protected areas and other forms of area-based conservation, on funding allocation. Finally, our data included funding committed up to 2013 (with some projects running till 2020s) and only in part of South America; expanding the efforts to more recent years and other regions can offer a more updated and complete picture. Yet, the issues we point out are equally (if not more) relevant today, including but not limited to the balance between carbon and biodiversity goals, and the unmet promise and opportunity of supporting IPLC.

5. Conclusions

International conservation funding for developing countries has recently increased in major ways, and the allocation of this funding to regions is an important step in identifying conservation priorities and implementing conservation interventions. Analyzing this allocation at the subnational scale for South America's major deforestation regions helped us to understand what drives this allocation, and thus explain possible matches and mismatches between priorities and interventions. In general, funding was committed to remote areas rich in biodiversity and carbon but not to areas with high levels of threat. Although growingly emphasized, IPLC lands were not yet an important factor in attracting international conservation funding. We also highlighted how the Amazon attracts international conservation funding from donors for local conservation needs and sometimes in adjacent regions. Together, our results emphasize the need for a more nuanced understanding of the factors attracting conservation funding, and the importance of subnational analyses in aligning conservation funding with conservation needs. The pressure on biodiversity is expected to increase and so is area-based conservation. Our work highlights the importance of better reporting and transparency of funding allocation, stronger coordinating funding priorities across scales, and integrating local values and concerns to address the ongoing biodiversity crises.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Siyu Qin: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data Curation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft, Reviewing and Editing. Marie Prater: Methodology, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft, Reviewing and Editing. Patrick Meyfroidt: Conceptualization, Writing – Reviewing and Editing, Supervision. Tobias Kuemmerle: Conceptualization, Writing – Reviewing and Editing, Supervision, Funding Acquisition.

Data availability

The data and code used in this paper are shared as supplementary materials.

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FIG. 1.

Spatial distribution of funding committed by the major donors (groups). The value of each pixel is for a $30 \text{ km} \times 30 \text{ km}$ grid cell at that location illustrated by the square icon. The thick green lines illustrate the biogeographical Amazon boundary (data from RAISG), and the dark gray lines illustrate the national boundary of the study area (data from GADM). *Funding volumes for the six maps are standardized separately; therefore, the means and standard deviations presented here are different across the maps. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

FIG. 2.

Influences of factors on funding committed through a) the entire study period 1987–2013 and b) after 2008 (i.e. 2009–2013), based on the best model (M2.4). Dots and horizontal bars show the mean and 95 % credible interval of the posterior distribution (shaded curve) of the estimated coefficient of the model predictor on conservation funding.

FIG. 3.

Spatial distribution of a) observed data and b) data simulated by the best-fitting model (M2.4). The value of each pixel is for a $30 \text{ km} \times 30 \text{ km}$ grid cell at that location illustrated by the square icon. The thick green lines illustrate the biogeographical Amazon boundary (data from RAISG), and the dark gray lines illustrate the national boundary of the study area (data from GADM). *For easier comparison, the mean and standard deviations used as breaks in both figures are based on observed distribution.

FIG. 4.

Comparison of the posterior predictive distributions (light blue line) and the observed data distribution (dark blue) when using the predictors from the final model for all funding to predict funding committed by a certain group of donors (bilateral donors in Europe, bilateral donors in North America, multilateral donors) and specific bilateral donors (second row). Better alignment between the observation and posterior predictive distribution curves suggests better model performance in explaining the observed distribution (e.g., for multilateral funding), while large discrepancies between the observed and model-predicted distribution curves (e.g., for funding from North America and Spain) means that the variables we modeled cannot explain the funding allocation. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

FIG. 5.

Conditional effects of factors influencing the allocation of funding committed to the two regions (Amazon vs. other regions outside the Amazon) by a) all donors, b) multilateral donors, c) bilateral donors in Europe, d) Germany, and e) Norway. Lines show the mean effect and 95 % credible interval (shaded area) of the posterior distribution when all model predictors, besides the one of interest, are set to their mean values. The results for North America and Spain are not reported here, as the posterior predictive check (Fig. 4) suggested that the model predictions for these donors were not robust.

TAB. 1.

Model comparison to assess the relative importance of factors explaining the allocation of international conservation funding. For each factor, we compared the set of models with combinations of relevant independent variables. We listed the models based on their performance, with the best-performing model listed first.

Factors	Model	Independent variables in the model ^a	Difference of expected log predictive density
Conservation targets	M1.3	species, carbon , forestloss, remoteness, IPLC	0
	M1.1	species , forestloss, remoteness, IPLC	-28.8; SE: 9.5
	M1.2	carbon , forestloss, remoteness, IPLC	-126.8; SE: 21.1
	M1.0	forestloss, remoteness, IPLC	-195; SE: 25.6
Threat	M2.4	threatened species, forestloss , species, carbon, remoteness, IPLC	0
	M2.2 (=M1.3)	forestloss , species, carbon, remoteness, IPLC	-9; SE: 6.6
	M2.3	forestloss, forestloss² , species, carbon, remoteness, IPLC	-9.2; SE: 6.6
	M2.1	threatened species , species, carbon, remoteness, IPLC	-19.8; SE:10.2
	M2.0	species, carbon, remoteness, IPLC	-27.3; SE:9.8
Cost	M3.1 (=M2.4)	remoteness , species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, IPLC	0
	M3.2	remoteness, remoteness² , species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, IPLC	-0.2; SE: 0.1
	M3.0	species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, IPLC	-35.1; SE: 11.7
IPLC lands	M4.0	species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, remoteness	0
	M4.1 (=M2.4)	IPLC , species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, remoteness	-1.6; SE: 0.2
Previous investment ^b	M5.1_wIPLC	grant_pre08 , species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, remoteness, IPLC	0
	M5.1_noIPLC	grant_pre08 , species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, remoteness	-3.9; SE: 4
	M5.0_wIPLC	species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, remoteness, IPLC	-6.2; SE: 6.5
	M5.0_noIPLC	species, carbon, species_th, forestloss, remoteness	-11; SE: 7.2